

Mechanical and Barrier Properties of Graphene Enhanced Carbon Fibre Composites

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Outline

- Background
- Sample preparation
- Mechanical properties
- Gas permeability - CO₂
- Future work

Background

Formula One MP4-30 (© McLaren)

A350 XWB (© Airbus)

Material service conditions:

- High pressure
- High temperature
- Corrosive environments

- Add nanomaterials
- Surface functionalization
- Modify fabrication methods

Challenges for traditional materials

FRP composites vs. metallic alloy:

- High specific strength/stiffness
- Corrosion resistant
- Efficient manufacturing

Shortcomings

- Delamination/Interfacial properties
- Brittleness
- Matrix properties

Aim:

Using graphene to improve the mechanical & barrier properties of FRP composites for structural applications.

Exploring sample preparation methods - GF

Spray coating (SC)

Vacuum mixed
Resin+1 wt.% M15

Resin infusion

Screen printing

Exploring sample preparation methods - CF

Spray coating (SC)

[0/90]
[±45]
[0/90]
[±45]
[±45]
[0/90]
[±45]
[0/90]

Control sample

Spray coating

Screen printing

Screen printing + Resin Infusion

Spray coating is selected for further investigations.

CFs spray coated with diverse loadings of GNP

1%

2.5%

5%

TGA of the Composites - W_f

GNP loading (%)	W_f
0	53.1%
0.25	52.2%
0.5	53.6%
1	53.1%
2.5	52.7%
5	54.3%

Mechanical properties

SEM images of the tensile fracture surfaces of the composites (a) without GNP, with (b) 0.25 wt.%, (c) 0.5 wt.% and (d) 5% wt.% GNP spray coated to the carbon fibres.

Mechanical properties

Flexural testing
ASTM D3039

Gas Permeability – CO₂

Future work

- Tube fabrication and characterization.
- Functionalization to improve the interfacial bonding.
- Effects of environmental conditions on the mechanical properties.
- Fatigue and creep properties evaluation.

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Thank you!

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